

1 **MAP kinase activation in TNBC.**

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6 We conducted an *in vitro* screen to identify genes associated with resistance in human TNBC cells to two
7 separate chemotherapeutic agents. *MAPK10* and *MAPK12* were among the kinases most significantly
8 activated. Other kinases were activated during resistance to chemotherapy, including STK17A.

9 Citations

- 10 1. Ying, J., Li, H., Cui, Y., Wong, A.H.Y., Langford, C. and Tao, Q., 2006. Epigenetic disruption of two
11 proapoptotic genes MAPK10/JNK3 and PTPN13/FAP-1 in multiple lymphomas and carcinomas through
12 hypermethylation of a common bidirectional promoter. *Leukemia*, 20(6), pp.1173-1175.
- 13 2. Gao, J., Liu, D., Li, J., Song, Q. and Wang, Q., 2016. Effect of STK17A on the sensitivity of
14 ovarian cancer cells to paclitaxel and carboplatin. *Oncology Letters*, 12(2), pp.1107-1112.
- 15 3. Short, S.P., Thompson, J.J., Bilotta, A.J., Chen, X., Revetta, F.L., Washington, M.K. and Williams,
16 C.S., 2019. Serine threonine kinase 17A maintains the epithelial state in colorectal cancer cells. *Molecular
17 cancer research*, 17(4), pp.882-894.
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